

Analysis of the Implementation of Drug Counseling as an Effort to Prevent Drug Abuse at Ketapang State High School

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the implementation of drug counseling as an effort to prevent drug abuse in Ketapang State High School. The focus of this research includes the implementation of counseling activities, its effectiveness in improving student understanding, and its influence on drug prevention behavior. This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive method. The research subjects consisted of students, teachers, and related parties at SMA Negeri 1, SMA Negeri 2, and SMA Negeri 3 Ketapang. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation and interviews, while data analysis uses an interactive model that includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawn. The results of the study show that drug counseling has been carried out through socialization activities, seminars, and cooperation with external institutions such as the National Narcotics Agency and the police. The counseling is able to increase students' knowledge and awareness about the dangers of drugs. However, its effectiveness in shaping preventive behavior is still not optimal. In the indicators of preventive behavior, students have shown the ability to avoid risky environments and have begun to be able to resist the invitation to drugs, although they are not yet fully strong. Meanwhile, when it comes to reporting drug abuse, students still show doubts and a lack of courage. This is due to the conventional extension methods and the lack of a participatory and sustainable approach. Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of drug counseling at Ketapang State High School has gone well in terms of knowledge, but it needs to be strengthened in the aspect of forming preventive behavior through more innovative, interactive, and life skills-based methods.

KEYWORDS: Adolescents, Drug Counseling, Drug Prevention, Student Behavior, School Education.

INTRODUCTION

The young generation is a strategic asset of the nation because the sustainability of national development is highly determined by the quality of human resources in the future (Setyaningrum, 2018). In the adolescent phase, especially high school students, individuals are at the stage of searching for their identity that is vulnerable to the influence of the social environment (Sartika, 2017). One of the serious threats facing the young generation today is drug abuse. Drugs not only have an impact on physical damage, but also damage the psychological, social, and future aspects of adolescent education (Sumara et al., 2017). This condition makes schools a strategic space in efforts to prevent drug abuse.

The phenomenon of drug abuse among adolescents is no longer limited to large urban areas, but has spread to various regions, including Ketapang Regency, West Kalimantan. Ketapang City has a large number of high school students with diverse social, economic, and cultural backgrounds. This diversity makes Ketapang a relevant context to study efforts to prevent drug abuse in the school environment. However, scientific studies that specifically examine the implementation of drug counseling in this region are still relatively limited.

Based on data from the Ketapang Police, in the last three years there has been a fairly high fluctuation in drug cases. In 2023, there were 96 cases, with 2 cases involving children. In 2024 it will increase to 117 cases with 1 child case, and in 2025 there will be 115 cases with 2 cases involving adolescents. This data shows that Ketapang Regency is an area with a fairly high rate of drug cases in West Kalimantan. These findings indicate that adolescents and students are still at risk of drug abuse, so more systematic and sustainable prevention efforts are needed through education.

One of the preventive efforts carried out in the school environment is through drug counseling activities (Humaini, 2021). Drug counseling is a form of education that aims to provide students with an understanding of the dangers of drugs, their types, and the impact they cause, so that students have awareness and the ability to stay away from drugs. However, in practice,

counseling often only focuses on delivering information cognitively, so it is not yet fully able to form deep awareness and preventive behavior in students.

Based on initial observations, drug counseling activities have been carried out in various high schools in Ketapang City. In this study, the researcher focused on the locations of SMA Negeri 1 Ketapang, SMA Negeri 2 Ketapang, and SMA Negeri 3 Ketapang. The three schools were chosen because they are public schools with a large number of students and diverse backgrounds. In addition, these schools have also carried out drug counseling activities, so it is relevant to further study their implementation in an effort to prevent drug abuse.

In various interactions with teachers and students, there are still inappropriate views related to drugs. Some students consider that drugs are a problem that is far from their lives or only related to a certain group. In fact, in reality, victims of drug abuse can come from various backgrounds, including outstanding students (Prawitasari, 2021). This shows that the counseling carried out has not been fully able to build comprehensive awareness in students.

Theoretically, drug abuse has a broad and complex impact. Physical impacts include nervous system disorders, decreased memory, and substance dependence (Yamin et al., 2024). Psychological impacts include stress, depression, and personality disorders, while social impacts can be seen from decreased academic achievement and increased deviant behavior Nova et al., (2024) It also states that adolescents who engage in drug abuse tend to experience weak social control and family dysfunction.

Previous research has shown that educational activities have the potential to increase students' knowledge and attitudes towards the dangers of drugs. Qolbiyyah et al., (2025) found that psychoeducation programs are able to improve adolescents' understanding and positive attitudes. Research by Askarial et al., (2025) It also shows an increase in student awareness after being given a drug prevention module. Other researchers by Suhita & Nugraheni (2022) states that prevention-based education in schools is effective in reducing risky behaviors. However, most of the research still focuses on outcomes (knowledge and attitudes), while studies on how the implementation of counseling is carried out in the field and how the process shapes students' preventive behavior is still not widely studied.

In addition, there are contextual gaps, where most of the research was conducted in large urban areas. Social, cultural, and geographical conditions in areas such as Ketapang have their own characteristics that can affect the process of implementing counseling and student acceptance of the material presented. Therefore, research is needed that examines the implementation of drug counseling based on the local context so that the results are more relevant and applicable.

This research has novelty in examining the implementation of drug counseling not only in terms of implementation, but also in relation to efforts to prevent drug abuse in students. This research is expected to provide a comprehensive overview of how drug counseling is planned, implemented, and the factors that affect its success in the school environment. Based on this background, the researcher is interested in raising the title "Analysis of the Implementation of Drug Counseling as an Effort to Prevent Drug Abuse at Ketapang State High School". This research is expected to make a theoretical contribution to the development of drug prevention education studies and become an evaluation material for schools and related parties in improving the quality of the implementation of drug counseling.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive type of research. This approach was chosen because the research aims to understand in depth how the implementation of drug counseling as an effort to prevent drug abuse in the school environment (Sugiyono, 2024). Through a qualitative approach, researchers can explore the phenomenon holistically and contextually based on the perspective of informants who are directly involved in drug counseling activities. The research was carried out in three public high schools in Ketapang Regency, namely SMA Negeri 1 Ketapang, SMA Negeri 2 Ketapang, and SMA Negeri 3 Ketapang. The selection of this location is based on the consideration that the three schools have carried out drug counseling activities and have diverse student characteristics, so that they are able to provide a comprehensive picture of the implementation of drug counseling.

The research subjects were determined using the purposive sampling technique, which is the deliberate selection of informants based on certain criteria relevant to the research objectives (Sugiyono, 2024). The informants in this study include school principals, teachers or student coaches involved in the implementation of drug counseling, as well as students as participants in counseling activities. The data sources used consist of primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained

directly through interviews and observations, while secondary data was obtained through supporting documents such as school activity programs, counseling implementation reports, and activity documentation (Sugiyono, 2024).

The data collection technique was carried out through in-depth interviews and observations. Interviews are conducted in a semi-structured manner so that the researcher still has a guide to questions but remains flexible in digging up information more broadly and deeply. Observations were carried out to directly observe the process of implementing drug counseling, including delivery methods, student involvement, and activity situations.

The data analysis in this study uses an interactive analysis model from Huberman & Miles (2002) which includes data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. Data reduction is carried out by selecting and focusing data that is relevant to the research objectives. Furthermore, the data is presented in the form of a descriptive narrative so that it is easy to understand. The last stage is the drawing of conclusions which is carried out in stages by verifying the data that has been obtained so that the results of the research can be accounted for.

To ensure the validity of the data, this study uses triangulation techniques, namely source triangulation and triangulation techniques. Source triangulation is carried out by comparing information obtained from principals, teachers, and students, while technical triangulation is carried out by comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation. Thus, the data obtained is expected to have a high level of trust.

The research procedure is carried out through several stages, namely the preparation stage which includes the preparation of proposals and licensing management, the implementation stage in the form of data collection in the field, the data analysis stage, and the preparation of research reports. All stages are carried out systematically so that the research can run well and produce findings that are valid and relevant to the research objectives.

RESULTS

1. Drug Counseling Planning

Based on the results of the research, the planning of drug counseling at SMA Negeri 1, 2, and 3 Ketapang is carried out as part of the school work program, especially in the field of student affairs and counseling guidance. Activity planning generally aims to provide students with an understanding of the dangers of drugs and form an attitude of rejection of drug abuse. The planned material includes the introduction of the types of drugs, health impacts, and legal consequences. However, activity planning is still general and has not been systematically arranged in the form of a long-term program that is integrated in a sustainable manner.

The results of the observation show that not all schools have detailed planning documents related to drug counseling. Some activities are carried out incidentally, especially when there is cooperation with external parties such as the police or related agencies. In addition, there was no syllabus or special modules that were used consistently in the implementation of counseling.

Based on the results of interviews with informants, it is known that the school is aware of the importance of drug counseling, but limited time and resources are obstacles in developing a more structured plan. Counseling guidance teachers stated that counseling activities often depend on programs from outside parties, so schools are not fully independent in designing activities in a sustainable manner. Thus, it can be concluded that drug counseling planning in the three schools still needs to be developed to be more systematic, directed, and sustainable.

2. Implementation of Drug Counseling

The implementation of drug counseling at SMA Negeri 1, 2, and 3 Ketapang is carried out through socialization activities involving resource persons from external parties, such as the police or related institutions. This activity is usually carried out in the form of lectures, material presentations, and educational video screenings about the dangers of drugs. The main purpose of this implementation is to provide understanding to students so that they can avoid drug abuse.

The results of the observation showed that the counseling activities ran in an orderly manner and were attended by students as a whole. However, the methods used tend to be one-way, so student involvement in activities is still limited. Most students only listen to the material without any active interaction such as in-depth discussions or Q&A. In addition, the relatively short duration of the activity caused the material presented to not be discussed thoroughly.

Based on interviews with informants, teachers and students stated that the counseling carried out was sufficient to provide information, but it was not interesting and did not fully involve students actively. Some students revealed that they understood

the material presented, but still had difficulty relating it to daily life. Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of drug counseling still needs to be improved, especially in the use of more interactive and participatory methods in order to increase student involvement.

3. Evaluation and Follow-up of Counseling

Evaluation and follow-up are an important part of the implementation of drug counseling. However, based on the results of the research, evaluation activities at SMA Negeri 1, 2, and 3 Ketapang have not been carried out systematically. After the counseling activities are completed, there is no special mechanism to measure the level of understanding or change in students' attitudes.

The results of the observation showed that there were no evaluation instruments such as questionnaires, tests, or written reflections used to assess the success of counseling activities. In addition, the follow-up carried out by schools is also still limited, usually only in the form of appeals or reminders to students to stay away from drugs.

Based on interviews with informants, the teacher stated that evaluations are usually carried out indirectly through observation of student behavior. Meanwhile, the students revealed that after the counseling activities were completed, there were no follow-up activities that specifically discussed the material that had been delivered. Thus, it can be concluded that the evaluation and follow-up of drug counseling is still not optimal and needs to be developed in order to support the success of the program in a sustainable manner.

4. Obstacles in the Implementation of Drug Counseling

In the implementation of drug counseling, there are various obstacles faced by the school. These obstacles include limited time, less varied counseling methods, and limited resources in the implementation of activities.

The results of observations show that counseling activities are usually carried out in a limited time and not routinely. In addition, the methods used tend to be monotonous, so they are less able to attract the attention of students to the maximum. Dependence on external resource persons is also one of the obstacles, because schools do not always have the opportunity to present resource persons on a regular basis.

Based on the results of interviews with informants, teachers stated that limited time in school schedules is the main obstacle in the implementation of counseling. Meanwhile, students revealed that counseling activities sometimes feel boring due to the lack of variety in the delivery of material. Thus, it can be concluded that obstacles in the implementation of drug counseling need to be a serious concern so that the implementation of activities can run more effectively and optimally.

5. The Impact of Drug Counseling on Students

Drug counseling aims to have a positive impact on students, both in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and behavior. Based on the results of the research, counseling activities have a fairly good impact on increasing students' knowledge about the dangers of drugs.

The results of the observation showed that students were able to understand the material presented, especially related to the types of drugs and their impact on health. However, changes in attitudes and behaviors have not been seen significantly.

Based on interviews with informants, students stated that they became more aware of the dangers of drugs after participating in counseling. However, some students still consider drugs to be a problem far from their lives. The teacher also said that although students' understanding has improved, real behavioral changes are still difficult to observe in the short term. Thus, it can be concluded that drug counseling has more impact on the aspect of knowledge than on changes in attitudes and behaviors, so a more comprehensive approach is needed in its implementation.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the implementation of drug counseling at SMA Negeri 1, SMA Negeri 2, and SMA Negeri 3 Ketapang has an important role in shaping students' preventive behavior, although its effectiveness still varies. In general, the counseling activities carried out have provided students with a basic understanding of the dangers of drugs, both from health, social, and legal aspects. This is in line with the opinion Princess (2021) which states that drug education is part of health education that aims to improve individual knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors to be able to make healthy decisions in

daily life. The findings of the study show that students are able to explain the definition of drugs, their types, and their impacts, which shows that the cognitive aspect of education has been achieved.

However, if examined more deeply on the aspect of preventive behavior, the results of the study show that not all students have strong abilities to implement preventive measures in real life. In the indicator of refusing drug invitations, some students stated that they were able to refuse firmly if faced with the situation, but there were still students who were hesitant or did not have full confidence. This condition is in line with the theory Enggarati & Santoso (2025) which emphasizes the importance of refusal skills as part of self-efficacy in dealing with social pressure. In addition, Syarif (2023) It also emphasizes that the ability to decline invitations is greatly influenced by social practice and real experience, not just knowledge. This means that counseling that is only informative is not enough to form strong rejection skills in students.

On the indicator of avoiding risky environments or people who use drugs, the results of the study show that most students have the awareness to maintain socializing. They tend to choose friends who are considered "safe" and stay away from potentially negative environments. These findings are in line with the opinion Hidayati (2024) which states that the social environment has a great influence on adolescent behavior, and Miftahusy'ian et al., (2020) which emphasizes the importance of maintaining social distancing as a form of preventive strategy. This shows that counseling has succeeded in shaping students' social awareness, although it still needs to be strengthened through continuous supervision and coaching from schools and families.

Furthermore, in the indicator of reporting drug abuse behavior, the results of the study show that students tend not to dare to report if they find indications of drug abuse in the surrounding environment. Some students feel scared, unsure, or think it's not their responsibility. This condition shows that the aspect of social responsibility has not been fully formed. In fact, according to Miftahusy'ian et al., (2020) Reporting is an important part of social control in creating a safe school environment. This indicates that the counseling carried out still does not touch the aspects of moral courage and social concern of students in depth.

If analyzed based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 2020) Students' preventive behavior is influenced by three main factors, namely attitudes, social norms, and self-control. The results showed that students already had negative attitudes towards drugs (disapproval of drug use), but social norms and self-control did not fully support strong preventive behaviors. For example, peer pressure and lack of experience dealing with real-life situations make students not fully ready to act. This reinforces the finding that knowledge-focused education is not enough to change behavior entirely.

In addition, from the perspective of Social Learning Theory (Enggarati & Santoso, 2025), students' behavior is greatly influenced by the social environment and the process of imitation. In the context of this study, students who were in a positive social environment tended to show better preventive behavior. In contrast, students who are in a less controlled environment have a higher risk of being exposed to negative behavior. This shows that the effectiveness of counseling is not only determined by the material delivered, but also by the supportive social environment.

In terms of implementation, counseling activities in the three schools are still dominated by the one-way lecture method, which tends to emphasize the delivery of information. These findings are in line with research (Askarial et al., 2025; Suhita & Nugraheni, 2022) which states that less interactive educational methods have limitations in shaping behavior change. In contrast, approaches that actively involve students such as peer education, group discussions, and simulations are considered more effective in building social skills and preventive behaviors.

Furthermore, if it is associated with the concept of health behavior (Nurlian et al., 2020; Prawitasari, 2021), drug prevention behavior includes not only aspects of knowledge (cognitive), but also attitudes (affective) and real actions (psychomotor). The results of the study show that these three aspects have not developed in a balanced manner. The cognitive aspect is good enough, but the affective and psychomotor aspects still need to be improved. This shows that the implementation of drug counseling in schools has not fully achieved its goals as a comprehensive prevention effort.

In addition to internal student factors, this study also found that external factors such as the role of teachers, schools, and related institutions also affect the effectiveness of counseling. Teachers have an important role as role models and facilitators in the formation of students' character, as stated by Suprayitno & Moefad (2024). However, the involvement of teachers in counseling programs is still limited to certain activities. Meanwhile, cooperation with external parties such as BNN and the police has been carried out, but not on an ongoing basis. This shows that cross-sector collaboration still needs to be strengthened so that drug prevention programs can run optimally.

Overall, the results of this study show that the implementation of drug counseling at SMA Negeri Ketapang has made a positive contribution in increasing student knowledge and awareness, but has not been fully effective in forming strong preventive behaviors. Therefore, it is necessary to develop counseling methods that are more innovative, participatory, and oriented towards the formation of life skills, such as the ability to refuse invitations, make decisions, and be socially responsible. Thus, drug counseling is not only an informative activity, but also able to form the character of students who are resilient and free from drug abuse.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion on "*Analysis of the Implementation of Drug Counseling as an Effort to Prevent Drug Abuse at SMA Negeri Ketapang*", it can be concluded that the implementation of drug counseling at SMA Negeri 1, SMA Negeri 2, and SMA Negeri 3 Ketapang has been carried out as part of preventive efforts in suppressing drug abuse among students. Counseling activities are generally carried out through socialization, seminars, and cooperation with external parties such as the National Narcotics Agency and the police, with a focus on delivering information about the dangers of drugs from health, social, and legal aspects.

From the results of the research, the counseling carried out was proven to be able to increase students' knowledge and awareness about drugs. Students in general have understood the definition, types, and negative impact of drugs on life. This shows that the implementation of counseling has been successful in the cognitive aspect. However, in the aspect of preventive behavior, the results of the study show that the effectiveness of counseling is still not optimal.

In the indicators of preventive behavior, it was found that students' ability to refuse invitations to use drugs has begun to form, but it is not yet fully strong in all students. When it comes to avoiding risky environments, most students have had the awareness to maintain socializing and stay away from individuals involved in drug abuse. Meanwhile, in the aspect of reporting drug abuse behavior, students tend to still be hesitant and do not have the courage and high social responsibility to report to the authorities.

In addition, the results of the study show that the counseling method used is still dominated by a one-way lecture approach, so it does not provide an active and participatory learning experience for students. This condition causes counseling to focus more on knowledge transfer than the formation of social skills and preventive behavior. Other factors that affect the effectiveness of counseling are the social environment of students, the role of teachers, and the involvement of external institutions that have not been carried out in a sustainable manner.

Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of drug counseling at Ketapang State High School has gone quite well in increasing student knowledge, but has not been fully effective in forming real preventive behaviors. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the aspects of methods, approaches, and collaboration so that counseling can produce more optimal behavior changes.

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